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"The good life is a process, not a state of being. It is a direction not a destination."

Carl Rogers

I believe this applies to teaching, being perfect is not the goal but improving certainly is.

Introduction

The starting point for this action research project was Wednesday 11/3/2020 as this was the last day the teaching staff and learners were allowed to work together in the same room. The Taoiseach Leo Varadkar announced that all educational facilities were to shut down as a requirement for public health and wellbeing due to the outbreak of potentially lethal disease Covid-19. The challenge created by this circumstance raised the question about how this writer was going to teach the QQI Rugby Coaching (Level 5) module without being in the same classroom or even the same training field as his learners. There was discussion among the staff about sending learning resources to learners via the postal system, but this was soon deemed unviable and inefficient. The only productive pathway available to deliver this module was to use distance learning known as e-learning. The Head of ICT (Information and Communications Technology) advocated for the use of Microsoft Teamstm as the online platform, which allowed our programme to continue. The Covid-19 crisis was the genesis for my critical question: How has an understanding of the QQI module Rugby Coaching's teaching and learning during the lockdown impacted my current practice and ideas about teaching?

I am a teacher and action researcher who works on behalf of the local Education and Training Board (ETB) on a joint programme with a major National Governing Body. This programme is dedicated to providing a sporting and educational experience for youth learners who complete a QQI major award in parallel with training in a professional football environment. This researcher has been employed on this course for over ten years. I would describe myself as feeling accustomed and well-adapted to the setting and the learners. However, I was not comfortable in facing the task of teaching a sports coaching module entirely online. I feared that I did not possess the technical skills to teach in an e-learning environment. This was an emergency situation, but the prime objective remained to create a learning experience which would lead to a formal qualification. This writer needed to understand existing research and how it relates to the critical question. This study is important because it shows how teaching online can be improved and how this writer gained insight into the evolution of progress as a teacher. Due to the unique nature of teaching a sports module entirely online during a Covid-19 lockdown, there is a lack of research to match the critical question directly. This study's rationale is to generate feedback from multiple perspectives such as personal reflections, from the learners, work colleagues, and relevant research literature. This is for the prime objective of enhancing the learning experience for the group. My beliefs are anchored in creating a learning environment that promotes educational curiosity and empowerment through engagement.

“Education isn’t something you can finish.”

Isaac Asimov

It is my ambition always to be curious to always increase my understanding.

Literature Review

Philips and Carr (2014, p.50) encourage the aspiring student-researcher to discover an area of focus. They assert that action research does not occur in a vacuum but "our friends, colleagues, students, administrators and extended community all play a role in forming our questions, designing our studies, and interpreting our results." Philips and Carr (2014, p.52) argue that the literature review has multiple benefits for a study such as assisting in creating the critical question and guiding the "analyse and interpretation of that data." A literature review is similar to “connecting with distance colleagues" Philips and Carr (2014, p.52). This researcher has integrated this concept into this study which is well suited to action research because it is based on teaching practice adapted to e-learning during the crisis caused by the Covid-19. This study has developed with the luxury of time that we reflect on the quality of the actions taken. It is built on reflection, guided by accurate analysis and views the learner's experience as central to progress. An assumption I apply to my teaching is that it can be improved. Lewin (1948, p.207) determines that action research is based on comparing research on the "effects of various forms of social action, and research leading to social action." Therefore, Lewin explains that research can lead to changes, but it also requires a change to occur. This researcher suggests that the idea of "action research, as a form of educational research, incorporates a commitment to act to bring about improved practices" (Lomax, 1995, p.50) is more relevant to a teacher seeking to improve their work in the classroom. This writer is concerned by the volume of material that must be covered in the time available. The pace is not conducive to learners discovering connections and ‘light bulb’ moments for themselves. Learners may be looking to this researcher to find the easiest way to get through assignments rather than seeking the answers for themselves.

This study is both an action research project and a self-study. This is a welcome opportunity to assess my strengths and note areas for development both in the online medium and in terms of my classroom teaching. The various data streams generated are based on Brookfield's (2017) four lens of becoming a critically reflective teacher theory. These lenses are autobiographical, learner's views, colleagues experience and the theoretical literature. These exist to offer feedback for reflection. Brookfield (2015) also considers how vital the relationship is between the learner and the teacher to achieve progress. Brookfield acknowledges he “cannot motivate anyone to learn if they don’t wish to ... but can build the best possible case for learning.” This writer understands that a teacher's role is a powerful one, but this power is rightfully limited and based on learners' cooperation. Knowles (2014) suggests that certain assumptions underpin the ability to add value to teaching through reflective practice such as readiness combined with the motivation to learn on the learner's part.

Brookfield (2015) encourages both teachers and learners to seek out assumptions and challenge them. For example in my reflective journal I noted "(Learner 7) 'Robert' continues not to contribute to class discussion unless asked a direct question. He does join in with group work but stays to the background allowing others to lead" (Lahiff, 22/10/2019). A later entry reads "I was pleasantly surprised to see 'Robert' score a distinction grade performance in his practical summative examination which I did not expect" (Lahiff, 11/12/2019). I was working on the assumption that if learners did not actively participate in group talk exchanges then they were not progressing as well as they could. 'Robert' proved me wrong in his case. Both Brockett (2018) and Palmer (2017) cite the requirement of reflection as a tool to gain self-knowledge. This generates an authentic teaching style which has caring for the learners as the foundation value for progress. Another educational theorist which this writer endeavours to emulate is John Dewey. He emphasised the importance of learning by doing and the essential requirement for reflection to improve teaching performance (Westbrook 2015). Dewey (1986, p. 247) argues "you cannot teach today the same way you did yesterday to prepare students for tomorrow." The writer believes that the need to assess teaching performance is a never-ending one. Learner needs and situations are ever-changing and require adaptation. There is no end to improving teaching, only learning.

This writer has sought to create a teaching and learning environment inspired by this study's philosophy of constructivism. Constructivism is based on the central idea that people construct new knowledge and skills based on their experiences (Fosnot 2013). Wilson (1996, p.5) similarly defines it as "a place where learners may work together and support each other as they use a variety of tools and information resources in their guided pursuit of learning goals and problem-solving activities." This writer considers constructivism as a learning objective-based task for learners rather than teacher-centric. Wilson (1996, p. 6) views the teacher's role as "coach and facilitator." This fits with facilitating learners to gain the skills to coach rugby football to underage players. For example, I generally demonstrate a skill, i.e. passing and challenge the learners to deconstruct (break down) its parts. Develop competency in performing the skill and then analyse how to teach it. Jonassen (1999) suggests that constructivism is best incorporated when learning outcomes are negotiated between teacher and learners, and when the evaluation is less goal-orientated. This researcher suggests that this particular design model for constructivism is challenging to match with the rugby coaching module since it has a set syllabus and summative assessment requirements.

Integrated into practice is the use of Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Chaiklin (2003) views this as having an essential connection to constructivism. They both rely on using the minimum level of intervention to enhance the learners' learning potential and require a knowledge of the learners to craft their learning environment. Warford (2011, p.253) defines ZPD as the "distance between what teaching candidates can do on their own without assistance and a proximal level they might attain through strategically mediated assistance from more capable others." The essence of ZPD is setting tasks which are demanding but achievable in the short term.

If the task demands too much of the learner and is perceived as too difficult, then annoyance, disinterest, and discouragement shall likely result. If the task appears too easy, the task difficulty is set too low; then there is little chance for progress.

The skill or knowledge is already known to them, so no challenge for mind or body is presented. In collaboration with learners, the teacher sets the task and hopes to set the demands at an optimal level to create a positive learning experience (Jones et al., 2018). The teacher will recognise this by seeing the learner absorbed in the task and applying old experiences to new situations. It is anticipated that learners will be curious for more knowledge about what has engaged them. De León (2012) observed how Vygotsky expertly combined ZPD with the use of scaffolding. This is the art of setting up a task with resources which allows the learner to explore and discover using their current knowledge and imagination (Hogan and Pressley 1997). Vygotsky identified scaffolding as what a learner “is able to do in collaboration today he will be able to do independently tomorrow” (Riber et al., 1987, p. 211). To explain how I use this model in my practice, I will use an example from the rugby coaching module. The group is given resources such as balls, cones and instructions for a drill (a modified game-like situation designed to reinforce the performance as a learned skill, e.g. passing or tackling.) Each learner is given a leadership turn to set up the drill. They must decide on the variables (space, ball numbers, tempo and precise rules) to decide how best their participants can best practise the rugby skill. After each turn, feedback is provided by their tutor. Students reflect on the experience and feedback and experiment again. Ballard and Bulter (2011, p.24) assert that ZPD is suited to integration with e-learning due to “its capacity for personalised learning and delivery of authentic and challenging tasks.”

There is value in reviewing the specific nature of e-learning. An online course (e-learning) is deemed to have more than 80% of its content delivered online (Allen and Seaman, 2010). It is acknowledged as an evolved form of distance learning (Palloff and Pratt, 2007). Diaz (1999) asserts that distance learning is a form of instructional delivery where the learners and teacher are in the same place. This researcher notes that it is curious that neither distance learning nor e-learning is directly addressed in the strategic goals for the SOLAS FET policy document 2014-2019. The primary benefit of using e-learning during the Covid-19 lockdown from 12/4/2020 was its ability to allow learners to continue their formal studies when the education facilities were physically closed (DES 2020). Another benefit for learners is "time freedom" this is especially so for asynchronous sessions where they are not required to attend a virtual classroom all at the same time. The resources are available online and can be engaged with at any time (Taylor 2002). Taylor acknowledges that e-learning is not suited to practical subjects such as surgery or sports skills. This certainly is relevant to this study dealing with rugby coaching skills. The nature of e-learning demands that learners take an active rather than passive role in acquiring new knowledge and skills. Zang et al., (2004, p.75) agree it is "learner-centred and self-paced." Knowles (2014, p.239) elaborates on this theme by emphasising that e-learning is compatible with a tasked based "learner-centred and collaborative mindset."

This writer notes that e-learning works with Knowles principles of adult learning, which encourages learners to use their experience and skills to completed tasks presented to them. This is a pathway for learners to combine their collective skills and knowledge to create innovations and solutions to tasks. Shang et al., (2001) support this view by observing that the constructivist learning model fits with e-learning by allowing learners to dictate the pace and construct new knowledge by themselves. Studies have found that e-learning can be a negative experience for learners.

Sims et al., (2002, p.141) allege the chief reason for this is an inability to design a course with "a balance of content, interaction and engagement." This is a typical result of what Phelan and Mulhall (2002, p.7) terms as the information dumping model. Lecturers put their notes into an online format without any effort for adaptation to the e-learning environment. This can result in a lack of engagement, boredom and confusion. Another factor for consideration is why the dropout rate for e-learning courses is higher than traditional courses. Herbert (2006) estimates this to be up to 20% higher for e-learning. Possible reasons for this put forward were motivational and social factors. Prominent from course design was the learner's need to interact with the teacher and fellow learners.

Huang at al. (2011) admits that research on e-learning being applied to sports coaching is limited compared to subject areas such as languages, science and mathematics. Traditionally e-learning was viewed as incompatible with practical subjects such as surgery, cooking and sports (Clark et al., 2016). Huang et al. (2011, p. 721) predict this situation to change because of the "development of E-learning platforms for physical education which integrates the different courseware within multimedia factors such as 3D animation, and digital video." This researcher suggests that the application of virtual reality (VR) can enhance this development through automated skill performance analysis and feedback. Reddan et al., (2016, p. 271) note that "computer technology has enabled an explosion in the availability of visual ways of presenting material, including large numbers of static images and dynamic images in the form of animation and video" in sports coaching courses. This follows the trend of visual images being superior to coaching courses instead of text for both learning and assessing. Reddan et al., (2016, p. 271) advocate the concept of the "flipped classroom." A topic is introduced by the learners using a multimedia file, for example a youtubetm video clip at home before class time. This means class time is not used to introduce the topic but for the teacher to engage their thoughts and feelings on it together.

"Not everything that can be counted counts, and not everything that counts can be counted."

Einstein

I believe it is vital for a teacher to note that they see in class and investigate why it is happening.

Methodology

This study's focus is not on the collection of numbers but exploring the meaning behind the data gathered. This work is an example of qualitative rather than quantitative research. Qualitative research is, "the systematic collection, organisation, and interpretation of textual material" (Malterud 2001, p. 483). It is best suited when the mere counting of an object or an incident provides insufficient meaning to create new knowledge or understanding. Jackson et al., (2007) view this method of data gathering to deliver "thick descriptive". It allows for a more in-depth exploration of thoughts and feelings concerning the study topic. However, it can also create more difficulty in directly comparing responses to indicate a general pattern. This is relevant to this writer's study because the goal was not to form a general theory but to gain data on how to improve my teaching performance best.

Watts (1985, p. 118) views action research as "a process in which participants examine their own educational practise systematically and carefully, using the techniques of research." This researcher suggests that this definition appears passive. It involves an internal view but holds no promise of change. Whitehead (1993, p. 44) declares action research to enable educators to realise their practice as part of "living educational theory generated from their own critical enquires." This is compatible with this writer's goal of not forming a general theory but a personalised theory from critical thinking of teaching and learning experiences. Lomax (1995, p. 49) offers a more straightforward definition suggesting that action research is an "intervention in practice to bring about improvement." She notes that the researcher "becomes both the subject and the object of the researcher driving the action." (Lomax 1995, p.51). This writer believes that there is a danger that the researcher can lose objectivity with such emotional and professional involvement. This is one reason why this study employs Brookfield's (1998) four lens of reflective practice to allow for multiple perspectives.

Data was gathered using various tools such as questionnaires, semi-structured interviews and a reflective journal. Foddy and Foddy (1994) acknowledge the inherent difficulty of achieving a high level of validity and reliability using questionnaires and qualitative research interviews. They reason that it is difficult to judge if the respondent takes the same meaning as the researcher intended. In this rugby coaching study, the questionnaire was accessed through a computer application (Survey Monkey[®]), so misunderstanding was possible. The chance of misunderstanding was less so in the semi-structured interviews because meaning could be tested through discussion between interviewer and interviewee. All the data sources add value to the study because they provide input from multiple perspectives.

They are generated from the researcher, group learners and fellow programme tutors. Jackson et al., (2007, p. 26) advise that good qualitative research requires a "high level of credibility and dependability." This can be enhanced with "audit trails and member-checking" (confirming the meaning of statements from interviewees) the goal being to facilitate "objectivity, ethical diligence and rigor."

Additionally, this work is a self-study. Samaras (2011, p. 1) defines a self-study as the "critical examination of one's actions and the context of those actions in order to achieve a more conscious mode of professional activity, in contrast to action based on habit, tradition, and impulse." I view this study as a prism to shine an investigate light not only on my teaching practice during the Covid-19 lockdown but to examine my evolution as a teacher. Clavijo Olarte (2016, p.9) reinforces the concept of using "teachers' autobiographies, personal-experience methods, teachers' narratives of their own practice, teachers' own teaching journals, and personal history-based beliefs relevant in teacher decision making" as data for a self-study. Glenn et al., (2012, p.10) while writing for the Irish Teaching Council saw it as grounded in the "researcher's educational values." This includes "collaboration" for educators who "work on their own but is always in the company of others." Lomax (1995, p.52) finds the requirement of educators to "interrogate their own values and examine the differences between values and practice." This self-study has tested if what I believe as a teacher is aligned with what I do as a teacher.

The creation of the critical question was a learning experience. Initially, my focus was only on how the learners were affected by completing a Rugby Coaching module entirely online. I believe this approach was born from my background in physiological studies. I was viewing the group as subjects and not accounting for my influence on circumstances. In discussion with work colleagues and my project Supervisor, they highlighted that I missed the opportunity for learning by not comprehending that this work should be a self-study and an action research project. This incident showed me the importance of dialogue with colleagues who have experiences that can add insight into my teaching. Brookfield (1998) refers to colleagues' experiences as the third lens as a method for a teacher to gain critical reflection. Permission to conduct the study was requested and granted by the authorities responsible for the educational facility in which I teach. Upon accepting my project supervisor's required ethics form, this researcher was given formal permission to research on 14/11/2020.

This study aligns with the Brookfield (1998) model of reflective practice. The reflective journal gives data for self-reflection. The questionnaire provides the views of the learners. The interviews gives voice to work colleagues. The fourth data source comes from exploring the academic literature, which relates to the study. By using multiple perspectives, this researcher aims to use triangulation to assure the validity of the research. This is a means to heighten a paper's credibility rating by comparing independent data sources relating to a single topic in common (Cohen et al., 2013).

Since the commencement of the Graduate Diploma in Adult Education programme, this writer has taken the lecturers' advice to maintain a reflective journal. A sample of the journal format is included in appendix 1. It contains three sections. The first describes a general area on how the teaching went on the day. The second features in point form what went well and what can be improved. The third details what specific action will be performed to progress the teaching experience for the learners.

This writer's preference is to handwrite the journal entries as opposed to using digital files. The period which covers the delivery of the rugby coaching module is from 8/4/2020 to 18/6/2020. The questionnaire (see appendix 6) was issued to twenty-three learners who are part of this group. Fifteen completed questionnaires were returned. Each learner was encouraged to explain each answer in full to facilitate the qualitative research process. This was conducted through a computer application (Survey Monkey[®]). The advantage of the application reduces learners' effort to complete and return compared to paper questionnaires. The researcher's advantage is that the application highlights the learners' keywords to aid thematic development for data analysis.

This writer conducted two semi-structured interviews with the other tutors who worked on the same programme and taught the same learners. They also taught QQI sport coaching modules (Basketball and Soccer) entirely online. This data collection method was done because only two were required and were viable under the study time restraints. They allow for "an increased level of detailed information in answers" and still "allow for a level of question standardisation for data reliability" (Woods, 2011). This writer suggests that having a face to face conversation can help the interviewee relax and reveal more relevant data. These interviews were conducted face to face but socially distanced as a standard Covid-19 precaution. The list of six questions can be found in appendix 2. Each interview lasted approximately thirty minutes as I explored their experience of teaching the modules and reflecting on their experience.

This writer has learnt a considerable amount from this process of data collecting from the various sources. The study confirmed that while I started teaching over a decade ago, it is now my career and one I happily intend to continue for my working life. The research has underscored the importance of reflection to improve and invigorate the practice of teaching. The task of analysing the data was informed by the work of Savin-Baden and Major (2014, p.11) who points out that "analysis involves uncovering patterns in data, and interpretation involves uncovering meaning." This researcher has followed the guidance of Phillips and Carr (2014) who advise that the first part of data analysis is to "divide the data into categories." Then this writer coded the data. This is to "reduce the data into meaningful segments and assign names" (Creswell, 2013). I then used the coded data to generate themes to discover findings. On reflection, if this researcher were to conduct this study again, the following would be done differently. Instead of using questionnaires to gather data from for the learners, I would use semi-structured interviews. The second change that I would make is to include all the tutors who taught this group during the covid-19 of 2020. I could then compare the data from tutors who taught sports modules to those who taught non-sports modules.

One of the limitations of this study was that the learner questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were done in November of 2020 about events in March and June of 2020. It is unknown if this time delay has degraded the quality of the data collected. A second limitation is whether the respondents gave truthful answers; they perhaps supplied answers which they believed the author expected. Efforts to mitigate this were the specific instruction on the questionnaire to express their honest thoughts and feelings

Findings

This section's topic for applied analysis is to discover the extent to which learners reacted to experiencing an online constructivist learning environment while taking the rugby coaching module. This requires a learner-focused approach where the teacher provides the task and resources to help achieve that task. The difficulty of the task is set at a level which allows them to progress using the scaffolding framework. "This is my first time leading a group where there will be no face-to-face class time. This made me feel anxious. Assignments with detailed instructions were set with support documents" (Lahiff, 2020, 14 April.) This does fit with the constructivist model as my role was to provide feedback to their efforts at task completion. It was interesting to observe that the other tutors shared this initial anxiety with the prospect of having no class or practical sessions. Tutor S termed it as "daunting." In comparison, tutor B used the word "dread" as his starting point. It is worth noting how we all shared this emotion, but none expressed it openly to each other. A thematic analysis to initially dealing with e-learning driven assignments highlighted the words "anxious, nervous" or "unprepared" from 12 out of 15 learner questionnaires. This demonstrates the stress level of all involved at the start of the process. Bawa (2016, p 4) warns that "if learners are not comfortable with self-learning and constructing knowledge out of their own initiatives, the online environment can become intimidating for them."

An important factor which relates to the learning environment is differentiation. This refers to content, process and product (Tomlinson,2000). Only process is in the control of the tutor as content (course syllabus), and product (how evidence is presented that learning outcomes have been achieved) is limited by certification requirements. Process details how the tutor guides the learner in engaging with the course material "Ironically, classes are not being held for this module yet I am spending at least triple the time engaging with the learners than when I had traditional class time" Lahiff, 2020, April 24). During the Covid-19 lockdown time, no synchronous online classes were held as I did not have the knowledge or group organisation to do so. I utilised the text messaging and voice call capacity of MS Team to give each learner assistance. The questionnaire shows that 14 of 15 learners used the direct messaging system. The thematic analysis shows that 12 out of 15 used the phrase "got stuck" or "ask a question" about using direct messaging regarding rugby coaching assignments. Tutor B stated that he did not use it due to not knowing the capacity exits (messaging text chat or voice call system in Teams™) while Tutor S reported in using occasionally. Marek (2009) describes e-learning as generally having less tutor to learner interaction than the traditional classroom environment. As a tutor teaching an e-learning course in an emergency, I felt obligated to promptly respond to learner messages. In the future, I would recommend using set hours for this to preserve an improved work-life balance.

E-learning cannot exist without a technological infrastructure to support it. Quality broadband access is essential for learners to access their assignments, resources and tutor. The learners in this group were scattered over two Munster counties in both urban and rural areas. According to the learner questionnaire, only out 1 out of 15 had difficulty accessing the learning platform due to a poor broadband connection. A larger issue was the question of what internet-enabled devices the learners could use to access course materials. 9 out of 15 had access to a desktop PC or laptop which left 6 only using their phones for this purpose. In a thematic analysis, all 6 used words "slow" "frustrating" "difficult" or similar to describe their feelings about this situation. "I only realised how hard it was for the learners to complete assignments on a phone when it was pointed out to me by learner number 4. How foolish I am for not considering this from their point of viewpoint." (Lahiff, 2020, April 17). From that point on, I made to effort to improve assignment format for phone only learners. Despite this, the assignments were made significantly more difficult by this disadvantage to the learner. This inequality needs to be addressed for the future if members of the teaching profession are aligning to the value of equal opportunity for learners.

It is appropriate to reflect on this researcher's strengths of practice in teaching the rugby coaching module during the lockdown. Central to the module's successful delivery (22 out of 24 learners gained certification) was establishing two-way communications with the learners.

I am lucky to have taught this group in a 'traditional' classroom for six months before lockdown and built a relationship with them. I can only imagine how harder it would be to teach entirely online without that foundation of trust (Lahiff 2020, April 23).

This is why they had the confidence to contact me and know they would get assistance with the day's course work task. Some learners only wish to ask an additional question on the text chat system while others require a collection of voice calls to keep them engaged and focused. This is differentiation in action and is adapted to individual learner needs. Studies depict a higher drop out rate of up to 20% for online groups versus traditional classroom-based groups (Herbert, 2006). This writer suggests that one reason we defied this statistic was the investment made in knowing and understanding the learners as individuals. I believe a constructive decision contributing to a successful outcome was the creation of a set routine. By 9.00 am, the tasks of the day and resources were posted for the group. Work was to be returned by 6.00 pm. This resulted in learners working on sub-goals each day and not being overwhelmed with course requirements at any one time. This practice fits with theories of scaffolding and use of zone of proximal development. This researcher believes this is why 14 out of 15 learners in the questionnaire indicated that the pace of work presented was correct. Tutor B astutely observed, "that the learners were forced to take more responsibility for their learning having to use family members for the skill demonstration...instead of using classmates they had to teach the skill to people that needed all the details explained to them." This has the positive social effect of involving family members in learning and requiring a more profound understanding to complete the task.

This researcher believes examining areas where practice can be improved to be an essential component of this work. An example being the reliance on course work based on text. This was a consequence of the original course based on printed folders. "After weeks working with the MS Teams system, I can see that I am using a small portion of its capacities." (Lahiff, May 12). With experience and formal training, I can increase multimedia, especially video clips and reduce reliance on text for presenting materials and learners providing evidence of learning outcomes. Hours spent on one to one assistance are not feasible for the future. This is why synchronous (learners attending simultaneously) online classes are required to support and deal with most of the issues learners may have with assignments for the course. One aspect of teaching that was not used in the online environment was mini-group work for the learners. This researcher values collaboration and views it as a powerful aspect of adult education, but online teaching skills limitations prevented it from being utilised. Younger learners are 'digital natives' and have grown up using multimedia such as computer and games systems and expecting a similar immersive experience in their education to be engaged (Prensk and Berry, 2001). This writer would advise caution in assuming that learners regardless of age, have a high level of digital literacy. Their needs should be assessed and digital skill training provided if required.

Recommendations

1. Implement synchronous (learners attending at the same time) online classes.
2. Create a library-style scheme that loan out learning technology devices, i.e. laptops to learners.
3. Staff training offered to enhance online teaching skills.
4. Increase the use of multimedia for summative assessment.
5. Set specific hours for a learner to expect a tutor to be available online to offer assistance.
6. Consider how course materials present on both PC, tablet and mobile phone formats.
7. Engage the 'flipped classroom' model.

Conclusion

This paper set to answer the question: How has an understanding of the QQI module Rugby Coaching's teaching and learning during the lockdown impacted my current practice and ideas about teaching? This was answered from multiple perspectives. The findings show that the researcher-teacher performed proficiently in an e-learning environment and what areas for future development are required. The findings' essence is that teaching in any circumstances is based on trust between learner and teacher to explore and grow. It shows the importance of reflection to seek improvement of teaching performance for the benefit of all. I look forward to using the 'flipped classroom' concept to add value to class time in engaging a topic and promoting collaboration. I have learned not to fear e-learning but to view it as a powerful tool to help learners explore and discover.

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Appendix 2

Tutor questions

1. What were your initial thoughts on hearing that you would be teaching a sports coaching module entirely online?
2. How did you expect the learners would react to the situation?
3. How did you go about forming a plan to teach the module?
4. What would you do in a different way if you were put in the same situation (teaching a sports module during lockdown) again?
5. Did you think the QQI (certification authority) guidelines for assessments during the lockdown was useful to you?
6. What new learning about teaching did this experience give you?

Appendix 3

Invitation letter to the organisation

To whom it may concern,

My name is Vincent Lahiff and I am currently doing the Graduate Diploma in Adult and Further Education in Mary Immaculate College, Limerick. A requirement of the course is to undertake an action research project which is also a self-study. The purpose of the study is to reflect and develop my own practice. I have decided to base my research on how has an understanding of teaching and learning of the QQI module Rugby Coaching during the Covid-19 lockdown impacted on my current practice and ideas about teaching?

As a participating organisation in the research project, the investigator would be required to meet with the participants before the interviews and questionnaire completion to brief them about the research project and its requirements. The investigator would seek to use a questionnaire to seek information from selected learners and interview two tutors and use reflective journaling to obtain data.

During the interview process, the tutors will be asked a series of semi-structured questions to obtain and develop information on the views and opinions expressed by the participant.

As the investigator for such a potentially beneficial topic, I assure you that any information that I collect from questionnaires and interviews is purely for research purposes. Information that is obtained from participants will remain confidential and anonymous. All information that is gathered will be encrypted and password-protected to ensure optimal protection. The research will not inflict any mental, physical or legal harm upon the participants and the organisation will remain anonymous to protect the relationship the organisation has with its service users.

Please find a consent form attached if you are accepting of the organisation to participate in the research project.

Feel free to contact me if you have any additional questions or if you would like to set up a briefing session on the action research process.

With regards

Appendix 4

Consent form student participants

I understand that I will be a participant in Vincent Lahiff action research project which will review the experience of completing a rugby coaching module. This will include a briefing session about the requirements of the action research project, activities and a semi-structured interview or questionnaire.

I also understand that my participation is completely voluntary and that I have the option to withdraw my consent at any time if I wish to do so. Since I am aware of the requirements of the action research project, I agree to participate in the briefing session and the interview or questionnaire. The investigator Vincent Lahiff has assured me that personal information that is gathered as result of this research will remain confidential and anonymous.

Therefore, I agree to be a participant in Vincent Lahiff action research project and its requirements.

Participant Signature _____ Date: _____

Appendix 5

Consent form educational facility

I understand that Vincent Lahiff will be conducting action research project which will review the experience of completing a rugby coaching module. This will include a briefing session about the requirements of the action research project, activities and a semi-structured interview or questionnaire.

I also understand that my participation is completely voluntary and that I have the option to withdraw my consent at any time if I wish to do so. Since I am aware of the requirements of the action research project, I agree to participate in the briefing session and the interview or questionnaire. The investigator Vincent Lahiff has assured learners that personal information that is gathered as result of this research will remain confidential and anonymous.

Facility Manager Signature _____

Date: _____

Appendix 6

Learner questionnaire

1. How prepared did you feel when informed you will be completing the course online instead of the traditional classroom format?

2. Did you have regular access to a computer with the Word software programme during the time away from your classroom?

3. Did the quality of your broadband connection affect your ability to access online course materials?

4. How easy to understand were the instructions for the assignments?

5. Was the speed with which your tutor presented the course material too fast, too slow, or about right?

6. Do you prefer to write your work, take a photo and upload it to Teams or submit directly to Teams using Word?

7. Did you use the personal message system on Teams to contact your tutor for assistance on course work?

8. Rate how prepared you feel to hold a mini rugby coaching session for players aged between 10-12 after completing this course?

9. What improvements would you suggest to the rugby coaching online course to make it a better learner experience?

Appendix 7
Instructions for Questionnaire

FAI LCETB E-learning Evaluation Survey.

Purpose:

1. To improve the learning experience for future course trainees.
2. Research study.

To make changes in the course for next year, please explain each of your answers as you genuinely feel and with as much detail as possible.

All information gathered will be anonymous.

Thank you.